

Keisen Associates Tokyo - Patent Litigation: Keisen Associates Wins for Garmin in Japanese IP High Court

On May 23, 2017, the Japanese Intellectual Property High Court (IPHC) ruled in favor of [Keisen's](#) client Garmin in a patent infringement claim brought by Pioneer (Case No H28(2016)(NE)10096). The IPHC not only unanimously rejected all of Pioneer's infringement claims but also rejected Pioneer's claims concerning the doctrine of equivalents and asserted that Pioneer's claims regarding operational features of Pioneer devices are in fact well-known technology.

Keisen also prevailed at the IPHC without disclosing any proprietary code or underlying algorithms for our client Garmin's devices. Instead, Keisen used a strategy of actual video field tests supported by affidavits and statements from Garmin engineers.

Keisen previously prevailed in the Tokyo District Court in 2016 under the same strategy, again without disclosing any trade secrets or proprietary algorithms.

Garmin is a leading developer and manufacturer of GPS and wearable technology, and our relationship with Garmin stems from our long

commitment to English language facing service and representing non-Japanese clients in Japan.